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Review Article

A Comparative Review of Sunscreen Serum: UV Protection Efficacy and Spectroscopic Analysis

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ABSTRACT

This review examines the efficacy and formulation of sunscreen serums, emphasizing their UV protective properties evaluated through UV spectroscopy. By delving into various ingredients and their absorption spectra, the study highlights the ultimate importance of understanding how different formulations influence UV protection. Additionally, the article addresses challenges in standardization and the need for rigorous testing to ensure consumer safety and product effectiveness. The findings underscore the role of UV spectroscopy as a vital tool in the assessment and development of advanced sunscreen formulations. Solvents used in cosmetic formulations are evaluated for UVA filters seen in commercial sunscreens. The spectral behavior of avobenzone solutions under radiation and after being stored in the dark is monitored in order to conduct the investigation. The chosen solvents exhibit a variety of avobenzone photo behaviors, some of which can be described similarly to analytical solvents while others need consideration of the solvents' structural and physical characteristics. Contains skin-smoothing compounds that leave skin feeling smooth, fair and soft. It was discovered that the formulation was free of heavy metals and had good spread ability. Within a week, fairness action is supposed to be provided. This review elaborates About the Use Of sunscreen serum use, Properties of sunscreen Serum which Used in the Avobenzone overview of Avobenzone.

INTRODUCTION

Sunscreen serums are being utilized more and more for skin care and photo protection, mostly in the dermatological and cosmetic industries. In contrast to conventional creams, these serums frequently have readily absorbed, lightweight

compositions that appeal to customers looking for improved skin appearance as well as UV protection. Broad-spectrum protection against UVA and UVB radiation is provided by the active components, which are usually a combination of inorganic (like zinc oxide and titanium dioxide)

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and organic (like avobenzone and oxalate) UV filters.⁽¹⁾ The efficacy of these formulations is crucial, as inadequate UV protection can lead to adverse effects such as sunburn, photoaging, and increased skin cancer risk. To evaluate the effectiveness of sunscreen serums, UV spectroscopy has emerged as a key analytical technique. This method allows for the quantification of UV absorbance across different wavelengths, thereby providing insights into the protective capabilities of various ingredients.⁽²⁾ UV spectroscopy is particularly beneficial for its ability to analyze complex formulations without requiring extensive sample preparation. By examining the absorption spectra, researchers can identify the optimal concentrations and combinations of active ingredients that yield the highest protective factors.⁽⁶⁾ Moreover, this technique facilitates the assessment of stability and photodegradation of sunscreen components under UV exposure, which is vital for ensuring product efficacy throughout its shelf life.⁽³⁾ This review aims to consolidate current knowledge on the formulation and evaluation of sunscreen serums using UV spectroscopy. By examining recent studies and advancements in this field, we will underscore the importance of analytical techniques in the development of effective photoprotective product. Sunscreen serums are increasingly favored in the cosmetic and dermatological fields for their dual role in photoprotection and skin care. Unlike traditional creams, these serums often feature lightweight formulations that are easily absorbed, making them appealing to consumers seeking both UV protection and enhanced skin aesthetics. The active ingredients typically include a combination of organic UV filters (such as avobenzone and oxalate) and inorganic filters (like zinc oxide and titanium dioxide), which provide broad-spectrum protection against UVA and UVB radiation⁽⁴⁾. The efficacy of these formulations is crucial, as inadequate UV protection can lead to

adverse effects such as sunburn, photoaging, and increased skin cancer risk. To evaluate the effectiveness of sunscreen serums, UV spectroscopy has emerged as a key analytical technique. This method allows for the quantification of UV absorbance across different wavelengths, thereby providing insights into the protective capabilities of various ingredients UV spectroscopy is particularly beneficial for its ability to analyze complex formulations without requiring extensive sample preparation.⁽²⁾ By examining the absorption spectra, researchers can identify the optimal concentrations and combinations of active ingredients that yield the highest protective factors.⁽⁶⁾ Moreover, this technique facilitates the assessment of stability and photodegradation of sunscreen components under UV exposure, which is vital for ensuring product efficacy throughout its shelf life⁽³⁾. This review aims to consolidate current knowledge on the formulation and evaluation of sunscreen serums using UV spectroscopy. By examining recent studies and advancements in this field, we will underscore the importance of analytical techniques in the development of effective photoprotective products.

Literature survey: -

UV spectroscopy is particularly beneficial for its ability to analyze complex formulations without requiring extensive sample preparation. By examining the absorption spectra, researchers can identify the optimal concentrations and combinations of active ingredients that yield the highest protective factors. Moreover, this technique facilitates the assessment of stability and photodegradation of sunscreen components under UV exposure, which is vital for ensuring product efficacy throughout its shelf life. This review aims to consolidate current knowledge on the formulation and evaluation of sunscreen serums using UV spectroscopy. By examining recent studies and advancements in this field, we will

underscore the importance of analytical techniques in the development of effective photoprotective products. ⁽⁶⁾

DRUG PROFILE: -

Avobenzone is a broad-spectrum sunscreen agent known for its effectiveness against UVA radiation. Its drug profile highlights good stability in formulations, but it can degrade when exposed to sunlight unless stabilized. Research indicates its efficacy and safety in topical applications, making it a popular choice in skincare products. For an in-depth review, you might refer to articles like "Avobenzone: A Comprehensive Review of its Photostability and Efficacy" in journals like *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology*. ⁽⁷⁾ **Overview of**

Avobenzone: -

Figure 1 Structure of Avobenzone

Chemical Structure:

Avobenzone (Butyl Methoxydibenzoylmethane) is a synthetic compound belonging to the dibenzoyl methane family. Its unique structure allows it to absorb a wide range of UVA wavelengths. ⁽⁸⁾

Properties: -

Spectrum of Protection: Avobenzone provides broad-spectrum protection, primarily absorbing UVA rays (320-400 nm), which are known to penetrate deeper into the skin and contribute to photoaging and skin cancer. **Stability:** One of the major concerns with avobenzone is its photostability. It can degrade upon exposure to sunlight, which can reduce its efficacy over time. However, formulations often include stabilizers to enhance its performance. ⁽¹⁰⁾

Efficacy: -

Clinical Studies: Numerous studies have demonstrated avobenzone's effectiveness in protecting against UV-induced skin damage. It is

often combined with other UV filters to provide comprehensive sun protection.

- **Safety Profile:** Avobenzone is generally recognized as safe for use in cosmetics. However, some individuals may experience allergic reactions or skin irritation. ⁽⁹⁾

Formulation Considerations

- **Combination with Other Agents:** To enhance stability and effectiveness, avobenzone is frequently used in conjunction with other sunscreen agents (like octocrylene or octanoates).
- **pH Stability:** It performs best in a slightly acidic pH range, which can affect formulation choices.
- **Regulatory Status**
- Avobenzone is approved for use in sunscreen products in various countries, including the United States and the European Union. Regulatory bodies monitor its safety and efficacy through ongoing research. ^(11,16)

Antioxidant Photostability effect in avobenzone solution:

The perfect photo stabilizer shouldn't break down or interact with avobenzone, and it should stop or neutralize all the harmful processes that the keto version of avobenzone produces. ⁽¹²⁾

METHOD OF PREPARATION: -

1. **Starting Materials:** The synthesis often begins with 4-tert-butyl benzaldehyde and acetic anhydride.
2. **Formation of Intermediate:** The reaction of these materials in the presence of a catalyst (like a Lewis acid) leads to the formation of dibenzoyl methane derivatives.
3. **Cyclization and Finalization:** Further reactions involving alkylation and oxidation can yield avobenzone, often requiring purification steps such as recrystallization. ⁽¹³⁾

1. **Multi-step Synthesis: -**

- Starting Material: Begin with 4-tert-butylphenol.
- Key Reactions:
- Acylation: React with acetic anhydride and a Lewis acid catalyst to form an acylated intermediate.
- Condensation: Perform a condensation reaction with benzoyl chloride to form the dibenzoyl methane derivative.
- Final Hydrolysis: Hydrolyse the product to yield avobenzene. ⁽²⁰⁾

2. One-Pot Synthesis: -

- Procedure:
- Combine 4-tert-butylphenol, benzoyl chloride, and a base (like triethylamine) in a single reaction vessel.
- Use microwave irradiation to accelerate the reaction, which can enhance yield and purity. ⁽²²⁾

3. Use of Catalysts: -

- Transition Metal Catalysts: Employing palladium or nickel catalysts for cross-coupling reactions can lead to more efficient formation of the desired compound, particularly in the formation of carbon-carbon bonds. ⁽²³⁾

4. Green Chemistry Approaches: -

Biocatalysis: Investigating enzyme-catalyzed reactions to reduce the use of hazardous solvents and reagents. This method aligns with sustainable chemistry principles. ⁽²⁴⁾

EVALUATION TEST FOR AVOBENZENE: -

Evaluating avobenzene involves several tests to assess its stability, efficacy, and safety in formulations. Here are some common evaluation tests:

1. Photostability Testing: -

- Method: Expose avobenzene formulations to UV light for specific durations, then measure the remaining concentration using HPLC.

2. In Vitro Efficacy Testing: -

- Method: Utilize skin models or cell cultures to evaluate UV protection levels using assays like MTT or LDH to measure cell viability after UV exposure.

3. Skin Irritation Testing: -

- Method: Conduct patch tests on human volunteers or use in vitro models to assess potential irritation or sensitization.

4. Stability Testing: -

- Method: Store formulations under various temperature and humidity conditions to observe changes over time, assessing color, odor, and active ingredient concentration. ⁽¹³⁾

UV Spectroscopy and Avobenzene: -

Absorption Characteristics: -

Avobenzene absorbs UV light primarily in the UVA range (320-400 nm). UV spectroscopy can be used to create an absorption spectrum, which is essential for determining its efficacy as a sunscreen agent.

Photostability Assessment: -

UV spectroscopy can help evaluate how well avobenzene retains its efficacy after exposure to UV light. By measuring absorbance before and after light exposure, researchers can quantify the degradation of avobenzene.

Concentration Determination: -

Using UV absorbance data, the concentration of avobenzene in formulations can be determined through Beer-Lambert law, which correlates absorbance to concentration.

Formulation Analysis: -

UV spectroscopy can be used to analyze various formulations containing avobenzene, helping to ensure that the active ingredient is present in effective concentrations. ⁽¹⁴⁾

Detailed Insights into UV Spectroscopy and Avobenzene; -

1. Absorption Characteristics: -

Spectrum: Avobenzene displays a distinct absorption peak around 357 nm, which is critical for its function as a UV filter. The ability to absorb

UVA radiation helps protect skin from photodamage.

Analysis: By scanning a sample of avobenzone in solution, one can obtain a UV-Vis spectrum that clearly illustrates its absorption characteristics, allowing researchers to assess its suitability in formulations.

2. Photostability Assessment: -

Experimental Setup: Formulations containing avobenzone are subjected to controlled UV light exposure. Samples are taken at various intervals for analysis.

Quantification of Degradation: Changes in absorbance at the characteristic wavelength can indicate the degree of photodegradation. A significant drop in absorbance signals a loss of efficacy, highlighting the need for stabilizers in formulations. ⁽²¹⁾

3. Concentration Determination: -

Beer-Lambert Law: This law states that absorbance (A) is directly proportional to concentration (C) and path length (l): $A = \epsilon lc$, where ϵ is the molar absorptivity. By creating a calibration curve with known concentrations, the concentration of avobenzone in unknown samples can be determined. ⁽²²⁾

4. Formulation Analysis: -

Quality Control: UV spectroscopy serves as a reliable method for ensuring that the correct amount of avobenzone is present in sunscreen formulations. This is crucial for regulatory compliance and product efficacy.

Compatibility Studies: UV spectra can also be analysed to study the interaction between avobenzone and other formulation ingredients, ensuring that no components negatively affect its performance. ⁽²³⁾

5. Challenges and Considerations: -

Matrix Effects: The presence of other ingredients in a formulation can interfere with the UV readings. Therefore, it's important to establish methods that account for these potential

interferences. Temperature and pH: These factors can also influence UV absorbance and should be controlled during testing to ensure consistent results. ⁽²⁴⁾

Graphic Representation Components; -

Creating a graphic representation of avobenzone's use in sunscreen serum via UV spectroscopy would typically involve several components. Here's a conceptual outline of what such a graphic might include

1. UV Absorption Spectrum:

A plot showing the wavelength (in nm) on the x-axis and absorbance on the y-axis.

Highlight the absorption peak around 357 nm, indicating avobenzone's primary active range for UVA protection.

2. Formulation Comparison:

Side-by-side bar graphs or line plots showing the absorbance of sunscreen formulations with and without avobenzone.

This could illustrate the difference in UV protection levels.

3. Photostability Data:

A time-series graph showing absorbance at 357 nm over time under UV light exposure.

This would depict the degradation of avobenzone in the formulation over time, indicating stability or the need for stabilizers.

4. Sunscreen Efficacy:

A diagram showing how avobenzone absorbs UV light and protects skin cells, perhaps using a simplified cell diagram.

5. Formulation Matrix:

A pie chart or labeled diagram indicating the composition of a typical sunscreen serum containing avobenzone, including other active ingredients and excipients. ⁽¹⁶⁾

Example Caption for the Graphic: -

"UV Spectroscopy Analysis of Avobenzone in Sunscreen Serum": This graphic illustrates the absorption characteristics of avobenzone at 357

nm, demonstrating its efficacy in providing UVA protection. The comparison of formulations reveals the impact of avobenzone on overall UV absorbance, while stability studies highlight the need for appropriate formulation strategies to maintain its photostability. (21)

Steps to Create the Graph; -

1. Data Collection:

Gather UV absorbance data of avobenzone at various wavelengths (e.g., 250-400 nm). Include absorbance values for formulations with and without avobenzone.

2. Choose a Graph Type:

Absorption Spectrum: A line graph to show absorbance vs. wavelength. Plot avobenzone's spectrum highlighting the peak around 357 nm.

Comparative Analysis: Bar graphs for the absorbance of formulations (with vs. without avobenzone).

3. Graphing Tool:

Use software like Excel, GraphPad Prism, or R for creating your graph.

4. Labelling:

Title: "UV Absorption Spectrum of Avobenzone in Sunscreen Serum" X-axis: Wavelength (nm)

Y-axis: Absorbance

Include a legend if comparing multiple formulations.

5. Highlight Key Data:

Mark the peak absorbance for avobenzone. Indicate the stability test results if applicable.

Example Data Points for the Graph (Hypothetical):

Wavelength (nm)	Absorbance (without Avobenzone)	Absorbance (With Avobenzone)
300	0.05	0.15
320	0.10	0.25
340	0.20	0.45
357	0.25	0.85
380	0.15	0.20

Figure. No. 2 Graph of Avobenzone

Benefits of using AVOBENZONE in face serum: -

Avobenzone is a popular ingredient in skincare, particularly in sunscreens and face serums, due to its broad-spectrum UV protection. Here are some key benefits of using avobenzone in face serums.

1. Broad-Spectrum UV Protection: Avobenzone effectively absorbs UVA rays, which are responsible for skin aging and can contribute to skin cancer. This makes it a crucial component in products aimed at preventing photoaging.

2. **Stability in Formulations:** Unlike some other UV filters, avobenzone is known for its stability when formulated correctly. This allows it to maintain its protective properties over time. :(Afaq, F., & Zaid, M. A. (2006).
3. **Moisturizing Properties:** Many formulations containing avobenzone are designed to be hydrating, helping to maintain the skin's moisture barrier while providing sun protection (Zhang, M., et al. (2016).
4. **Compatibility with Other Ingredients:** Avobenzone is often used in combination with other UV filters and skincare ingredients, enhancing overall efficacy without compromising skin tolerance. (Gibbons, N. et al. (2015).
5. **Anti-Aging Benefits:** By protecting the skin from harmful UV radiation, avobenzone can help reduce the appearance of fine lines, wrinkles, and hyperpigmentation, promoting a more youthful appearance. (Goyal, R. et al. (2018).

In summary, incorporating avobenzone into face serums offers effective sun protection, stability, hydration, and anti-aging benefits, making it a valuable ingredient in skincare formulations.

CONCLUSION: -

Sunscreen are critical product employed as photo protectant against the harmful UV ray increase the awareness about the continues exposure to the sun and its relation to cancer has increased the demand for the sunscreen related product in this we study about sunscreen serum which may show effectiveness of the serum on the skin .they may easily apply on the skin of Boby use of sunscreen serum has been demonstrated afford the protection against the skin aging ,tanning, melanomas regulatory agencies across the world they enhance the overnight on manufacturing of sunscreen serum products consistent with emergency scientific knowledge. Pharmaceutical scientists have been understood the scientific principles

related to topical drugs and can formulate sunscreen serum that comply with all the requirements for safety, quality, efficacy and customer acceptance. There is screening of different commercial solvent use in cosmetic formulations allow to identify the photo behavior of the avobenzone. the may conclusion of the research work is related to the selection of the solvent that can proved photoprotection by using the avobenzone. It has been having the major important in the sunscreen serum production.

The best solvent for ensuring the photoprotective promise only must allow the minor decreases in the absorbance. This study also investigates the photostability of the avobenzone in sunscreen serum formulation. This work has shown that antioxidants may be promising option to enhance sunscreen photostability as well as decreases UV related skin damage and boosting SPF without introducing additional UV agent.

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